

MEDICAL SCIENCES

PERIODONTAL REACTIVITY, METABOLIC PROCESSES AND CARIES RESISTANCE IN ADOLESCENTS

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The physiological balance of the processes of re- and demineralization of enamel, the maintenance of the processes of resorption and growth of bone tissue are carried out due to the balance of macro- and microelements. When considering this balance in the age aspect, you come to the conclusion that this constant is quite dynamic. Numerous experimental and clinical studies confirm that the most unstable indicators of mineral metabolism are characteristic of the age of 12–15 years. E.V. Udovitskaya, U.A. Parley (1989) call this period “physiological dysgorionosis.” It is this age group that is characterized by a high prevalence, intensity and significant increase in caries (E.M. Kuzmina, 1998) and during this same period the eruption and active mineralization of a large number of permanent teeth (premolars, canines, second molars) occurs. In addition to all of the above, it is at this age that poor oral and dental hygiene is most often observed (A.M. Khamadeeva, 1987) and the resulting plaque contributes to the demineralization of “immature” enamel (Binus W. Et al., 1987). What is the reason for refusing to pay due attention to oral hygiene? It should be noted that adolescence, with its sociopsychological adaptation, places sharply increased demands on the entire body. According to R. Raha, I. Flostad et al. (1974), the intensity and pathogenic significance of chronic stress depend on the speed and nature of life changes that deviate the individual’s existence from everyday stereotypes and attitudes. According to the scale of life-changing units (LIU) they developed, many events (change of occupation and place of residence associated with study, employment, appearance and change of sexual partners, conflicts associated with integration into the hierarchy of teenage groups) are considered very stressful. So, for example, entering a study is equated to changing jobs and according to the scale of R. Rahe et al. corresponds to 36 GIU (for comparison, the death of a spouse or parent corresponds to 100 GIU). Meanwhile, when the limit of 75 FIE is exceeded in six months, the likelihood of diseases of impaired adaptation increases significantly, which in a certain way can affect the construction of a motivational hierarchy by a dentist. One should not diminish the significance of anamnesis data characterizing a disorder in the regulation of the body’s balance constants (75% of children suffer from this in prepuberty, 85% in puberty) [3]. These may be neurocirculatory dystonia, low-grade fever, general weakness, irritability, borderline hypertension, depression,

which characterize the tense regulatory relationships of the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal systems (O.V. Volkov, 1983). Apostol P. (1998) considers these conditions as a stress status, the indicator of which is an increased content of catecholamines in the urine. Against this background, it is often possible to trace an imbalance of micro- and macroelements, which is inextricably linked with the function of regulatory systems - endocrine, nervous and immune. The manifestation of this kind of failure can be a decrease in local immunity of the oral cavity, a change in saliva viscosity and, as a result, a decrease in caries resistance and an increase in the reactivity of periodontal tissues [1]. The pedantry of the relationship between micro- and macroelements in adolescence coexists, according to the classical data of K. Klotubücher (1944), with a surprisingly high tolerance to glucose compared to all older age groups. The ability for such pronounced insulin production in healthy adolescents is not accidental. This hormone is the most important growth and anabolic factor (V.N. Nikitin, 1975) and takes an active part in the processes of regulation of calcium-phosphorus metabolism, processes of mineralization of the bone skeleton and tooth enamel. The most important elements that ensure the full structure of tooth enamel, an adequate reaction of the bone tissue of the jaws and periodontal tissues are calcium and phosphorus, as well as their ratio - Ca/P coefficient. During puberty, intense processes of formation and mineralization of bone matter occur. This places increased demands on the system for regulating this process. The role of the essential trace element calcium is difficult to overestimate. The generation of action potentials and electromechanical coupling, the transmission of hormonal signals, the life span of the cell and its apoptosis depend on calcium [3]. The metabolism of calcium in the body is closely intertwined with the metabolism of phosphates, which bind most of the extracellular calcium in the form of hydroxyapatite crystals. 98% of calcium and 85% of phosphorus are bound in bones and teeth [4]. Normally, the concentration of calcium in saliva is 1.4 mmol/l, which is present in several fractions: about half is in the form of ionized Ca²⁺, about 1/3 is represented by protein-bound Ca and the remainder is contained in complex compounds with citrate, phosphates and other anions (G.B. Sagulis et al., 1985). The phosphorus content in unstimulated saliva reaches 1.9–7.7 mmol/l (with an average value

of 6.0 mmol/l). Salivary phosphorus is mainly in ionized form and is presented in the form of inorganic compounds and only 5% in the form of pyro- and orthophosphate [5]. In puberty, according to research by I.V. Kobiyasova et al. (2003), one can trace the low effectiveness of local methods of preventing and stabilizing caries disease (rational oral hygiene and protective coating of hard tooth tissues with fluoride varnish). This is confirmed by the increase in the caries intensity index 12 months after the initial examination by more than 2 times. It is important to note that according to research by N.A. Savushkina (2003), in adolescents with a compensated form of caries, the share of the ionized calcium fraction of saliva accounts for 58.8%, and in adolescents with sub- and decompensated caries - 80.2%. The identified interfractional distribution of calcium is due to the fact that adolescents with multiple carious lesions of hard dental tissues experience an increased release of calcium from the salivary glands to maintain salivary homeostasis (T.P. Redinova, 1989), as well as the adverse effects of acidified dental plaque. Against the background of these disorders, the risk of developing new carious lesions sharply increases, and the risk of disruption of the functioning of the bone remodeling unit or basic multicellular unit (BMU) is also quite high. The BME is a section of bone tissue in which time-coupled processes of local resorption and bone formation occur. In a balanced organism, each bone remodeling unit is a constant in time of formation and in number. 100 μm of bone is resorbed in 30 days (L. Ya. Rozhinskaya, 2001), and is replaced by 100 μm of new bone in about 90 days, i.e. a full cycle takes about 4 months. In the presence of inflammation in periodontal tissues, the time for restoration of new bone increases in the best case, and in the worst case this does not happen at all [2, 4]. These aspects are very important to consider when managing an orthodontic patient during puberty. How is bone metabolism and mineral metabolism regulated? This is a whole hierarchy of internal secretion organs, the coherence of the functioning of which determines the adequacy of the macroorganism's response to external intervention, in particular orthodontic and therapeutic manipulations. The complex regulatory relationships of a teenager's body can be aggravated by the state of diselementosis, which is caused not only by a lack or excess of substances, but also by a violation of their optimal ratios in the diet. It should be noted that the state of calcium-phosphorus deficiency is promoted by a high-protein diet, due to increased calciuria and secondary calcium balance [6]. A woman who smokes 12 cigarettes a day is at risk of a decrease in estrogen in the blood, which entails increased leaching of calcium from bones and enamel. Daily consumption of 2 cups of coffee is associated with a daily calcium loss of up to 6 mg [5, 6]. A marker of mineral metabolism disorders, namely calcium-phosphorus balance, is menstrual dysfunction. The latter may be caused by anorexia nervosa, a disease of

young people. But even with a favorable outcome - an increase in body weight and restoration of menstrual function, women in the future constitute a risk group, since they do not gain sufficient peak bone mass [6]. When collecting an anamnesis, it is important to clarify whether there are any disturbances in the activity of the thyroid and parathyroid glands, pancreas (are they registered at the endocrinology clinic), whether there was surgical intervention for oophorectomy, whether kidney diseases, gastrointestinal tract are registered, whether they are taking anticonvulsants (the latter cause various disorders of mineral, bone metabolism and vitamin D metabolism), phenacetin-type analgesics. The optimal calcium intake during puberty is 1200 - 1500 mg per day. Calcium is poorly absorbed in the gastrointestinal tract. It belongs to the difficult-to-digest elements. The daily diet, provided that 1-2 glasses of milk and 100 g of cottage cheese are consumed, contains no more than 600-900 mg of Ca [6].

Calcium content in food (in mg per 100 g of product): Dairy products: milk 3% - 100, yogurt - 120, milk 1% - 120, dietary yogurt - 85, cottage cheese - 95, sour cream - 100, goat cheese - 300, processed cheese - 300, hard cheeses - 600. Green vegetables: Lettuce - 83, cabbage - 60, Celery - 240, onions - 60, Beans - 40, olives - 77. Bread: Rye - 60, wheat - 30. Fruits and nuts: oranges - 35, dried apples - 45, figs - 57, dried apricots - 170, raisins - 56, almonds - 254, peanuts - 70, sesame - 1150, pumpkin seeds - 60, sunflower seeds - 100. Fish and meat: fish dried with bones - 300, sardines with bones - 350, boiled fish - 20-30, beef - 10-30. Thus, the puberty period is a rather difficult age period both for the patient and for the dentist or orthodontist. The doctor needs to analyze not only "de facto" data that allows for rapid diagnosis. For complete sanitation, both therapeutic and orthodontic, it is necessary to take into account the elements of the manifestation of all organs and systems directly or indirectly involved in the processes of regulation of caries resistance and periodontal reactivity.

References:

1. Kotova S.M., Karlova N.A., Maksimceva I.M., Zhorina O.M. Formirovanie skeleta u detej i podrostkov v norme i patologii. — Posobie dlja vrachej. SPb., 2002 — S.44.
2. Onoprienko G.A. Vaskuljarizacija kostej pri perelomah i defektah. — M., 1995 — S. 14.
3. Stroev Ju.I., Churilov L.P. Jendokrinologija podrostkov. — SPb, 2004. — S. 227-228.
4. Alponar E. et al. // J. of Dental Reseach. — 1999. — V. 78-A. — P. 1337-1347.
5. Philip M. et al.// J. of Dental Reseach. — 2000. — V. 90-F. — P. 1467-1487.
6. Eitel F. et al. // Nutrition Journal. — 2002. — V. 30 A. — P. 358-420.